

Metal Complexes of Peptide Derivatives. Part-XII. Mixed Ligand Complex Formation of Copper(II) with Salicyloylglycylglycine and some Typical N-Donor Ligands

G. N. MUKHERJEE* and S. K. CHATTERJEE

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009

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Equilibrium study on the complex formation of copper(II) with salicyloylglycylglycine, (*o*)-HO-C₆H₄-CONH-CH₂-CONH-CH₂-COOH (LH₂), in the presence of typical ligands, such as bipyridine, ethylenediamine and benzimidazole (A) by pH-metric and spectrophotometric methods has provided evidence of formation of binary and ternary complexes of the types, Cu(A)²⁺, Cu(H₂L)²⁻ and Cu(A)(H₂L)²⁻. Stability constants of the complexes have been determined pH-metrically in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at a constant ionic strength, *I* = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃) at 25 ± 1°. Complex formation equilibria are elucidated on the basis of speciation curves and the modes of coordination of salicyloylglycylglycine in the binary and ternary complexes are discussed.

Mixed ligand complex formation equilibria of metal ions with amino acids and small peptides in the presence of typical ligands provide models for metal-protein interactions in metalloenzymes¹. The influence of the presence of an adjacent C=C bond on the protonation and metallation equilibria of the peptide bond (-CONH-) and the influence of the presence of COOH and phenolic OH groups in adjacent positions on the modes of metal ion coordination of the peptide bond have been described earlier^{2,3}. The present communication describes the results of equilibrium study on the mixed ligand complex formation of copper(II) with the peptide derivative, salicyloylglycylglycine, (*o*)-HO-C₆H₄-CONH-CH₂-CONH-CH₂-COOH (hereafter, SGG or LH₂) (1), in the presence of typical ligands, such as bipyridine (bipy), ethylenediamine (en) and benzimidazole (bz), hereafter (A). Proton-ligand and metal-ligand equilibria have been studied by pH-metric titration method⁴ in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium maintaining a constant ionic strength, *I* = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃) at 25 ± 1°.

Results and Discussion

In the absence of Cu^{II} ion the ligand SGG titrates as a biprotic acid (LH₂) due to successive deprotonation of the COOH and the phenolic OH groups ($pK_{\text{COOH}}^{\text{H}} = 3.93$, $pK_{\text{OH}}^{\text{H}} = 8.35$). The two amide (-CONH-) moieties remain neutral in the absence of Cu^{II} ion in the entire pH range (pH 2–12) studied.

In the presence of Cu^{II} ion, in the binary systems (Cu^{II} : SGG = 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 5), deprotonation of the COOH

Fig. 1. pH-metric titration curves : (1) 0.01 M HNO₃, (2) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.002 M Cu(NO₃)₂, (3) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.01 M SGG (LH₂), (4) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.01 M SGG (LH₂) + 0.002 M Cu(NO₃)₂, (5) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.002 M SGG (LH₂) + 0.002 M bipyH₂²⁺ + 0.002 M Cu(NO₃)₂, (6) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.002 M SGG (LH₂) + 0.002 M enH₂²⁺ + 0.002 M Cu(NO₃)₂, (7) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.002 M SGG (LH₂) + 0.002 M bzH⁺ + 0.002 M Cu(NO₃)₂, initial volume = 25 ml, titrant : 0.125 M NaOH.

group occurs in the same pH range (3.0–4.5) as it occurs in the absence of Cu^{II}. This is followed by another buffer region (pH 4.5–7.5), involving the release of 3 mol of H⁺ per mol of Cu^{II} (Fig. 1), with the appearance of an intense red-violet colour (λ_{max} 540 nm) that is characteristic of Cu^{II} ion in a square-planar [Cu(N-amide)₂(OOC)(O)] geometry¹. Such a square-planar structure (2) may result from

Fig. 2. Speciation curves of ternary Cu^{II}/SGG(LH₂)/bipy system : (1) bipyH₂⁺, (2) bipyH⁺, (3) LH₂, (4) LH⁻, (5) Cu(bipy)²⁺, (6) Cu(H-₂L)²⁻, (7) Cu(bipy)(H-₂L)²⁻, (F_M) Cu²⁺.

coordination of Cu^{II} by the two deprotonated amide N-atoms along with the deprotonated phenolate O-atom and possibly also by the carboxylate O-atom of the ligand, SGG. Although the buffer region corresponding to deprotonation of the COOH group of SGG is not lowered in the presence of Cu^{II} ion, indicating noninvolvement of the COO⁻ moiety in coordination, but chelation of Cu^{II} by the two deprotonated amide N-atoms and the phenolate O-atom certainly disposes the COO⁻ group in a sterically favoured position for coordination, and possibly this is how a square-planar [Cu²⁺(N,N,O,O)] structure (2) results. The 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : SGG stoichiometry of the resulting binary complex has been confirmed by spectrophotometry following molar ratio method⁵ at 540 nm. Thus the complex formation equilibria of Cu^{II} with SGG (LH₂) in binary system may be represented according to the following equilibria,

$$K_{\text{Cu+LH}}^{3\text{H}} = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{H-}_2\text{L})] [\text{H}]^3}{[\text{Cu}] [\text{LH}]} \quad (2b)$$

Charges are not shown in the expressions for clarity. The H-₂L⁴⁻ ion in the Cu^{II} complex represents the fully deprotonated SGG ligand species. The right-hand subscript (-2) after H signifies that the two amide (-CONH-) protons of the ligand LH⁻ remain neutral in the absence of Cu^{II}, but these are released due to coordination of amide N-atoms to Cu^{II}.

As the buffer region corresponding to the hydrolytic equilibria of Cu²⁺(aq.) ion overlaps with the buffer region corresponding to the complex formation equilibria of Cu^{II} with the SGG ligand at the latter stages (Curve 2, Fig. 1), both in the binary Cu^{II}/SGG as well as in the ternary

Fig. 3. Speciation curves of ternary Cu^{II}/SGG(LH₂)/en system : (1) enH₂⁺, (2) enH⁺, (3) LH₂, (4) LH⁻, (5) Cu(en)²⁺, (6) Cu(H-₂L)²⁻, (7) Cu(en)(H-₂L)²⁻, (F_M) Cu²⁺.

Cu^{II}/SGG/A systems with A = bipy, en and bz, so the formation of the hydroxo complexes, Cu(OH)⁺, Cu(OH)₂ have also been considered in calculating the stability constants of Cu^{II}-SGG and Cu-SGG-A complexes. Concentration of Cu²⁺ has been kept sufficiently low so that the solubility product of Cu(OH)₂ is not exceeded. Proportions of these hydroxo complexes are, however, negligible in the ternary systems with A = bipy and en.

The Cu(bipy)²⁺ ion has been the only copper containing species at pH <5 in the ternary Cu^{II}/SGG/bipy system (Fig.

Fig. 4. Speciation curves of Cu^{II}/SGG(LH₂)/bz system : (1) bzH⁺, (2) LH₂, (3) LH⁻, (4) Cu(bz)²⁺, (5) Cu(OH)⁺, (6) Cu(OH)₂, (7) Cu(H-₂L)²⁻, (8) Cu(bz)(H-₂L)²⁻, (F_M) Cu²⁺.

2). The binary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{SGG}$ complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$, has been found to be practically non-existent in the entire pH range. The ternary complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$, exists as the sole copper containing species above pH 7. Speciation curves of LH^- , $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})^{2+}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$ indicate the formation of the ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$ complex according to the equilibria,

$$K_{\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}} = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{L})][\text{H}]^3}{[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})][\text{LH}]} \quad (3b)$$

Although $\text{Cu}(\text{en})^{2+}$ is the major copper containing species at pH > 2.5 in the ternary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{SGG}/\text{en}$ system, small amount of the binary $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$ complex is also found to be formed. Speciation curves (Fig. 3) indicate the formation of the ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$ complex mainly according to equilibria of the type (3a) and also according to the reproportionation equilibria⁶,

$$10^{\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}} = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{L})][\text{Cu}]}{[\text{Cu}(\text{en})][\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{L})]} \quad (4b)$$

The ternary complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$, is the major copper containing species above pH 7.

The ternary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{SGG}/\text{bz}$ system is remarkably different from the ternary $\text{Cu}/\text{SGG}/\text{A}$ systems with $\text{A} = \text{bipy}$ and en . All the possible binary species, viz. $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})^{2+}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$ are found to exist in this system (Fig. 4). Speciation curves of $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})^{2+}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$, LH^- and $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$ indicate the formation of the ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$ complex both according to equilibria of the type (3a) and (4a) in the pH range 5–7, but its concentration never exceeds 10% of total copper. The binary complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$, is the major (~90%) copper containing species above pH 8.

The output of the computer program scogs⁷, does not give the constants, $K_{\text{CuA}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}}$ (eqn. 3b), but gives the overall constants, $K_{\text{Cu}+\text{A}+\text{LH}}$ which may be defined as

$$K_{\text{Cu}+\text{A}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}} = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{H}_2\text{L})][\text{H}]^3}{[\text{Cu}][\text{A}][\text{LH}]} \quad (5b)$$

This overall constant, may be related to the constants $K_{\text{CuA}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}}$ and $K_{\text{CuA}}^{\text{Cu}}$ according to eqn. (6),

$$\log K_{\text{Cu}+\text{A}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}} = \log K_{\text{CuA}}^{\text{Cu}} + \log K_{\text{CuA}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}} \quad (6)$$

where, $K_{\text{CuA}}^{\text{Cu}}$, stands for the stability constant of binary complexes, CuA , $\text{A} = \text{bipy}$, en , bz , as may be defined as

$$K_{\text{CuA}}^{\text{Cu}} = \frac{[\text{CuA}]}{[\text{Cu}][\text{A}]} \quad (7b)$$

The constant, $K_{\text{CuA}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}}$ may be calculated with the aid of eqn.(6) using the computer refined values (Table 1) of the constants $K_{\text{CuA}}^{\text{Cu}}$ and $K_{\text{Cu}+\text{A}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}}$. Similarly, the reproportion constants, $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ may be calculated using the relation,

$$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}} = \log K_{\text{Cu}+\text{A}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}} - \log K_{\text{CuA}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}} - \log K_{\text{CuA}}^{\text{Cu}} \quad (8)$$

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND Cu^{II} -LIGAND BINARY AND TERNARY CONSTANTS OF $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{SGG}(\text{LH}_2)/\text{A}$ SYSTEMS ($\text{A} = \text{bipy}$, en AND bz)

Temp. = $25 \pm 1^\circ$, Medium : 50% (v/v) ethanol-water,
 $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3)

(a) Proton-ligand constants :

	bipy	en	bz	SGG(LH ₂)
$\text{p}K_2^{\text{H}}$	2.28 ± 0.02	6.29 ± 0.04	–	3.93 ± 0.02
$\text{p}K_1^{\text{H}}$	3.37 ± 0.03	8.82 ± 0.04	5.56 ± 0.04	8.35 ± 0.04

(b) Hydrolysis constants of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{aq.})$ ion :

	$\log K_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{H}}$	$\log K_{\text{Cu}}^{2\text{H}}$
	-5.94 ± 0.04	-12.00 ± 0.06

(c) Cu^{II} -ligand binary constants :

	$\log K_{\text{CuA}}^{\text{Cu}}$
$\log K_{\text{Cu}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}}$	
A	
bipy	8.00 ± 0.04
en	10.84 ± 0.04
bz	3.26 ± 0.04

(d) $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{SGG}/\text{A}$ ternary constants :

A	bipy	en	bz
$\log K_{\text{Cu}+\text{A}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}}$	-5.05 ± 0.03	-3.71 ± 0.03	-10.39 ± 0.04
$\log K_{\text{CuA}+\text{LH}}^{3\text{H}}$	-13.05 ± 0.04	-14.55 ± 0.04	-13.65 ± 0.04
$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$	$+0.80 \pm 0.04$	-0.70 ± 0.04	$+0.20 \pm 0.04$

$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ values characterise the coordination tendency of LH^- to $\text{Cu}(\text{A})^{2+}$ ion relative to $\text{Cu}^{2+}(\text{aq.})$ ion⁶. The $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ values (Table 1) of $\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$ complexes are found to be in the order : $\text{bipy} > \text{bz} > \text{en}$, with regard to the A ligands. Combined π -acidic and σ -basic nature of bipy and bz ligands produces stronger metal-ligand bonds than those formed with en ligand, which is σ -basic only. Delocalization of π -electron density of Cu–N bonds over to the heteroaromatic π -systems of bipy and bz gives enhanced stability of the $\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$ complexes with these two ligands as compared to en. The extent of such π -electron delocalization with the (N,N) bidentate bipy ligand is certainly higher than that with the N-monodentate bz ligand.

As the strongly coordinating bipy and en ligands occupy two positions around the square-planar Cu^{II} ion, the most likely mode of coordination of the SGG ligand species, H_2L^{4-} , should be (N,N) bidentate coordination through the two deprotonated amide N-atoms to provide a square-planar $\text{Cu}(\text{N})_4$ geometry (3) to the ternary complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$, with $\text{A} = \text{bipy}$ and en . However, the possibility of axial coordination by the carboxylate and phenolate O-atoms can not be ruled out. N-Monodentate coordination by the bz ligand to the square-planar $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$ complex (2) possibly gives a square-pyramidal geometry (4) to the ternary complex $\text{Cu}(\text{bz})(\text{H}_2\text{L})^{2-}$.

Experimental

The ligand SGG was prepared by condensing acetylsalicyloylchloride with glycylglycine in alkaline medium (pH 9) followed by acidification and subsequent hydrolysis of the resulting acetylsalicyloylglycylglycine, when salicyloylglycylglycine (SGG) was obtained as shining white crystalline needles. The product was crystallized from aqueous ethanol according to the procedure described earlier³.

All the other reagents were of A.R. grade. Solutions for the equilibrium study were prepared in double-distilled CO₂-free water and purified ethanol⁸. Copper nitrate solution was prepared by dissolving freshly precipitated copper hydroxide in nitric acid and was standardized by complexometric EDTA titrations, ion exchange separation and acid-base titrations⁹.

Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out with a Hitachi U 3501 spectrophotometer. pH measurements were made with a Systronics 335 pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) using the combination of a special glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode. The pH meter was calibrated using aqueous buffer solutions of pH 2.0, 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2. Analytical concentrations of hydrogen ion were obtained from the pH meter readings after incorporating corrections for the use of mixed solvent¹⁰. Activity coefficient of hydrogen ion and ionic product of water under the experimental condition were obtained from literature¹¹.

Solutions having following compositions (all concentration in mol dm⁻³, *M*), were prepared for pH-metric titrations : (i) 0.01 *M* HNO₃, (ii) 0.01 *M* HNO₃ + 0.002 *M* Cu(NO₃)₂, (iii) 0.01 *M* HNO₃ + 0.01 *M* SGG (LH₂), (iv) 0.01 *M* HNO₃ + 0.01 *M* SGG (LH₂) + 0.002 *M* Cu(NO₃)₂, (v) 0.01 *M* HNO₃ + 0.002 *M* SGG (LH₂) + 0.002 *M* bipyH₂²⁺ + 0.002 *M* Cu(NO₃)₂, (vi) 0.01 *M* HNO₃ + 0.002 *M* SGG (LH₂) + 0.002 *M* enH₂²⁺ + 0.002 *M* Cu(NO₃)₂ and (vii) 0.01 *M* HNO₃ + 0.002 *M* SGG (LH₂) + 0.002 *M* bzH⁺ + 0.002 *M* Cu(NO₃)₂. Initial volume of each solution was 25 ml. Required amounts of NaNO₃ were added to all these solutions to have a constant ionic strength, *I* = 0.1

mol dm⁻³. All the solutions were allowed to attain the equilibrium at the experimental temperature $25 \pm 1^\circ$ (thermostated), and titrated with a standard 0.125 mol dm⁻³ carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution¹². To ensure the exclusive formation of the simplest ternary complexes, Cu(A)(H₂L)²⁻, the ratio of Cu^{II} : SGG : A was kept at 1 : 1 : 1 in the ternary mixtures (v)-(vii).

Stability constants of the complexes formed in the solutions were calculated with the aid of the computer program SCOGS⁷, in FORTRAN 77. pH, volume (of titrant NaOH) data from the smooth titrations curves drawn through the experimental points were supplied to the computer as input data. Refined values of the constants (Table I) were used to calculate the speciation curves, which were the basis of elucidation of the complex formation equilibria prevailing in the solutions.

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